

**ALTERNATIVE INSTRUCTIONAL PRACTICES OF SOCIAL STUDIES
TEACHERS IN TEACHING PHILIPPINE HISTORY: A
TRANSCENDENTAL PHENOMENOLOGICAL
APPROACH**

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Alternative Instructional Practices of Social Studies Teachers in Teaching Philippine History: A Transcendental Phenomenological Approach

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Abstract

The study aimed to explore the elementary Social Studies teachers' lived experiences in utilizing alternative instructional practices in teaching Philippine History, the problems, and challenges they encountered, the factors that teachers consider in selecting and utilizing instructional practices, and the contexts and situations that influence their experiences. This transcendental phenomenological study used Moustakas' method of data analysis to interpret and analyze the data. Nine (9) teachers participated in the study recruited through purposive sampling technique. The study utilized semi structured interview method in the gathering data. The study revealed that the experiences of teachers in utilizing alternative instructional practices promote effective teaching and learning. The problems and challenges experienced by the participants include ineffective instructional strategy, lack of instructional and learning materials, insufficient time, and students' attitudes. The factors that the participants considered in choosing and utilizing instructional practices include students' levels and abilities, time, classroom setting, availability of instructional and learning materials, and topic or content. Furthermore, students' performance and motivational level were the contexts and situations that affected their experiences in utilizing alternative instructional practices. The findings of this study can be used as a springboard for school leaders in conceptualizing seminars and training to improve the alternative instructional practices of Social Studies teachers in teaching Philippine History.

Keywords: *alternative instructional practices, social studies teachers, Philippine History*

Introduction

Education is the means that fosters learning or the acquiring of information, abilities, moral values, beliefs, and practices. With this notion, the 1987 Philippine Constitution states that the goal of education is to "foster a love of humanity, respect for human rights, appreciation of the role of national heroes in the historical development of the country". To achieve this goal the K-12 Basic Education Curriculum through Republic Act 10533, provides the way to a Social Studies Curriculum that is more extensive which mandated the teaching of Philippine History to Grade 5 and Grade 6 students as an introduction and foundation of the study of Philippine History.

Philippine History is one of the subjects under Social Studies which its primary objective is the creation of democratic citizens (Cebe, 2020). In addition, Tallavaara and Rautiaine (2020) described and emphasized the relevance of history as a collection of narratives that students should learn to comprehend the present and to develop a cohesive perspective of the past to become tolerant people and engaged citizens who can critically question information.

The researcher believed that the success of the implementation of any educational program depends on the instructional practices teachers utilize in teaching.

Research studies were conducted to describe the instructional practices of teachers in teaching Philippine History however, these research studies revealed that teachers continued to employ traditional style of teaching, lacked teachers' historical expertise and instruction and teachers placed more emphasis on memorization (Cebe, 2022; Alic & Bual, 2021; Sarbiani, et al 2019). In addition, Lucero (2021) stressed that many students found Social Studies uninteresting, so teachers in the Philippines struggle to find ways to inspire students to learn.

On the contrary, there were also research studies about instructional practices in teaching Social Studies and Philippine History on how it promotes students' academic achievements, effective teaching practices, and integration of 21st Century strategies into Social Studies education (Francisco & Celon, 2020; Pangilinan, 2021).

Most of these research studies were conducted in secondary schools and higher education through a quantitative and qualitative method and focused on students and teachers as their participants.

With the contexts and situations mentioned, the researcher believed that there was a need to conduct a research study in the elementary grades wherein this level of schooling serves as the introduction and foundation of Philippine History as mandated by the K-12 Curriculum. This research study focused primarily on elementary teachers handling Philippine History to explore the "what of their experiences in utilizing alternative instructional practices, the various influences they considered in choosing and utilizing instructional practices as well as to describe the "how" of their experiences through a transcendental phenomenological approach to improve the status and quality of teaching Philippine History to achieve the goal of the Social Studies K-12 Basic Curriculum which was to develop productive citizens of the country.

Research Questions

The study aimed to explore the experiences of social studies teachers in teaching history of the Philippines in the Division of City Schools, District of Caloocan South. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of Social Studies teachers in utilizing alternative instructional practices in teaching Philippine History?
2. What are the problems/challenges the Social Studies teachers experienced in utilizing alternative instructional practices?
3. What are the various influences and factors that Social Studies teachers considered in choosing and utilizing alternative instructional practices?
4. How do the Social Studies teachers describe the contexts or situations that influence their experiences in terms of the phenomenon?

Literature Review

Alternative Instructional Practices

Teaching is a method of communication between teachers and pupils. As teachers communicate to students in teaching, teachers utilize varied instructional practices to plan, carry out plans, and evaluate teaching. According to Francisco and Celon, (2020), instructional practices include a diversity of techniques, like organizing the physical environment, creating rules and procedures, preserving students' attention to the lessons, and commitment to activities. Furthermore, these instructional practices are a set of teaching strategies and methods of instruction employed by the teacher in the classroom to achieve the desired teaching and learning objectives (Kalu-Uche, 2015, in Clores and de España, 2023). Kloser (2014 in Clores and de España, 2023) believed that effective teaching is guided by specific instructional practices.

In addition, Saleh and Ai Jing (2020) defined instructional practices which refer to the actions taken by the teachers in developing the lesson. They stressed that it is the teachers' characteristics and behaviors that lead their classes and consistently use them over time. How the teachers plan their instructions into a sequence of events, presenting the lesson, asking questions, demonstrating skills, and evaluating performance are all parts of their instructional practices (Saleh & Ai Jing, 2020).

Dancy and Henderson's Framework (2007 cited in Saleh and Ai Jing, 2020) identified types of instructional practices which include traditional and alternative instructional practices. Alternative instructional practices are simply referred to as student-centered teaching approach, a style of instruction that is responsive, collaborative, problem-centered, and democratic in which both students and the teachers decide how, what, and when learning occurs (Dupin-Bryant, 2004; Dancy & Henderson, 2007; Horvat-Samardzija, 2011; cited in Saleh & Ai Jing, 2020). Alternative instructional practices center around learners' encounters points of view, interests, capabilities, and needs.

In the 21st century, teachers also use instructional practices with the help of computer aided instructional methods and social media applications like video clips available via YouTube to make their instructional practices appealing to the students at present times. According to Aydogmus et al. (2023), there was enough practical, and helpful educational content on social media. Furthermore, in the study by Ilther (2022), teachers believe that technology satisfies their students' demands for learning in social studies, and employing technology for a variety of tasks and in diverse ways may increase students' perceptions of the worth of learning social studies content. To keep all students interested, technology has also proven to be a lifesaver for teachers (Lucero, 2021).

Experiences of Teachers in Utilizing Instructional Practices

There were research studies conducted that described the experiences of teachers in utilizing alternative instructional practices in different aspects and perspectives. Teachers experience that effective instructional practices were related to students' accomplishments, performance, and learning process.

In the study of Francisco and Celon (2020) instructional practices affect students' academic achievement to varying extents in Social Studies and other subjects. In addition, Francisco and Celon, (2020) also expounded that instructional practices can stimulate students learning and help them concentrate and merge information for understanding and remembering. Furthermore, the integration of 21st Century strategies into Social Studies education shows even more promise for these approaches as a means of enhancing and transforming social studies education (Pangilinan, 2021).

Research studies about the experiences of teachers in utilizing alternative instructional practices also affect students' attitudes toward the subject as experienced by teachers. One of which was Awa-ao and Roperez's research from 2024 which indicated that promoting historical appreciation and localizing historical teaching were two of the beneficial experiences teachers had. The participants in the same study experiences also revealed that students who engage in the study of local and national History cultivate a more profound admiration for their hometowns and an enhanced comprehension of their historical background (Awa-ao & Roperez, 2024).

In the study of Alic and Bual (2021), the top best practices in the teaching and learning process of Philippine History were connecting the lesson to current social issues and the use of technology and multimedia tools in teaching. Aydogmus et al. (2023) mentioned that

students benefited from teachers using social media for instructional objectives; these beneficial outcomes include engaging, motivating instruction, positive attitude development and heightened interest, sustained attention, and academic performance.

On the other hand, there were also research studies that cited the experiences of teachers in assessing students' performance as highlighted by Noor et al. 2020; Bordoh, 2022 (cited in Asante, et al. 2023) which stated that teachers assess students' progress, and they can implement a rapid feedback process in the classroom, which leads to positive outcomes in their work and inspires learners to study the target.

With the impact of utilizing instructional practices utilized by teachers in teaching History experienced as mentioned in the research studies, Zaka and Muhammad (2020) highlighted that to improve the effectiveness of their instruction, teachers should reassess their methods and strategies of teaching to make it more interesting and appealing to students. Ali et al. (2023) also stressed that teachers should employ a variety of activities to keep the class's attention on the learning process, get learners interested in what they are learning, apply and practically apply lessons to real-world scenarios, and enhance students' comprehension of the subject matter to meet goals and objectives.

Challenges and Problems in Utilizing Alternative Instructional Practices

In utilizing instructional practices, teachers also experience problems and challenges. According to the study of Dizon, et al (2019) in the implementation of K-12 curriculum, teachers experience problems. Teachers lacked the necessary number of textbooks, learning aids, and even electronic materials. The participants in the study deemed that textbooks and learning resources are important aids in utilizing instructional practices. These problems revealed by Dizon et al. (2021) were supported by Sumaljag's (2020) study, which revealed that one of the challenges in implementing the K-12 curriculum was the lack of necessary materials, teachers struggled with the lack of textbooks, activity sheets, and other learning resources. In this situation, enough resources should be provided for teaching and learning, and additional funding should be set aside for the acquisition of educational materials. These claims were also supported by a study conducted in 2024 by Awa-ao and Roperez, who discovered that a lack of learning resources and a scarcity of Philippine historical books made it difficult for participants to comprehend and carry out the lessons. Teachers also face the difficulty of finding trustworthy sources to effectively integrate and discuss topics related to local history.

Aside from the problems and challenges with the educational resources, there were also research studies conducted to describe the state of teaching Philippine history at various levels. According to a study by Alic and Bual (2021), students who are enrolled in the Reading in Philippine History course face several difficulties, including a lack of background knowledge in the subject, a narrow discussion scope for required topics, and a gap between the subjects assigned and teachers' fields of expertise. Teachers' field of expertise as a problem was elaborated by De Loreto et al. (2019) study, which brought out that new graduate teachers lacked pedagogical content knowledge. Furthermore, Awa-ao and Roperez's study from 2024 expounded the claims of Alic and Bual (2021) and De Loreto et al. (2019), which stressed that the challenges rely on teachers' insufficient historical understanding, which is a result of their undergraduate degrees. According to the study, every participant earned a bachelor's degree in elementary education (BEED) but did not specialize in Philippine or local history during their undergraduate studies.

Research studies abroad also had a similar argument made when it comes to teaching History in schools abroad. Anis et al. (2020), citing Sarbiani et al. (2019), emphasized that the study of history in high schools is still conventional and does not foster intellectual abilities. History teachers place more emphasis on memorizing a long list of names of historical figures and the dates and years of significant events, which may or may not be meaningful to the students, this condition makes students far from the process of awareness and becomes only an imitation of the teacher.

Student factor is also a problem and challenge in teaching Philippine History and in utilizing instructional practices. Awa-ao and Roperez's research study from 2024 showed that students' low historical knowledge and comprehension was one of the problems with teaching local history due students' immaturity causes them to ignore and forget History lessons. This is supported by the study of Domingo (2021) that has drawn attention to the major risks connected to the decline of historical perspective and the declining significance of Philippine history. This problem makes it difficult for them to teach the subject (Awa-ao & Roperez, 2024).

Despite of the mentioned problems and challenges, Awa-ao and Roperez (2024) noted in their study that innovative approaches were employed to solve the difficulties and guarantee effective instruction to overcome the obstacles in teaching Philippine and local history. Teachers demonstrated inventiveness, images, films, videos, and PowerPoint presentations are frequently utilized by teachers as teaching tools. Furthermore, collaborative teaching emerged as a critical answer, as a result DepEd Districts' intervention, which encouraged teacher collaboration (Awa-ao & Roperez, 2024).

These problems and challenges should be addressed to make the teaching and learning process of Philippine History promote understanding and appreciation and appeal to students. The researcher believes that this could be possible through exploring the alternative instructional practices of teachers in teaching Philippine History.

Various Influences on Teachers' Instructional Practices

With the mentioned definition and description of instructional practices as well as the experiences of teachers in utilizing instructional practices, it is important to explore the various influences on teachers' conception of utilizing alternative instructional practices.

Conception is the term used to describe any mental construct in an individual teacher that potentially provides a rationale for a particular instructional practice. Conceptions have been shown to be instrumental in defining tasks and selecting cognitive tools with which to interpret plan and make decisions regarding such tasks; hence they play a critical role in defining behavior and organizing knowledge and information (Dancy and Henderson, 2007, cited in Saleh and Ai Jing, 2020).

Furthermore, Ilther (2022) noted that teachers' particular choices regarding what to teach, how to teach, and what students should learn in Social Studies classes appear to be influenced by their own beliefs. This is because the way in which teachers have characterized their classrooms seemed to be influenced by their goals for teaching social studies.

With this notion, the researcher believed that teachers' conceptions and beliefs influence them in choosing and utilizing instructional practices which may include students/learners, time, and environment of learning as well as instructional materials and learning resources and the content or lesson. This notion was supported by Ali et al. (2021), as they stressed that the choice of a certain approach is influenced by the learning objectives, the subject matter, and the needs, interests, and capabilities of the students.

It is a common knowledge that students/learners are the primary reason of teaching and learning. This is the reason why students should be one of the factors to consider in choosing and utilizing instructional practices. This is supported by DepEd's K-12 Basic Education Programs, according to DepEd the defining characteristic and guiding principle of this curriculum is learner centeredness

Time is another factor to consider in utilizing instructional practices. According to UNESCO's International Institute for Educational Planning, to maximize student engagement and learning, schools require enough days and hours for instruction as well as qualified teachers who can provide high-quality lessons.

Aside from the students or learners and instructional time, another factor is the place or environment. The classroom is seen as the center of activity for the entire process of teaching and learning. A warm and accommodating learning environment can be created by teachers by being flexible in their pedagogical techniques and instructional strategies to meet the needs of every student. It enables students to have unique and meaningful learning experiences that increase their motivation, engagement, and academic progress (Putzer, 2023). Thus, teachers should do their best to make the classroom conducive for learning wherein all students are included and recognized in the activities to maintain harmonious relationships (Zaka & Muhammad, 2021)

Another factor to consider in choosing and utilizing instructional practices is the learning resources and teaching materials, tools that both teachers and pupils can use to enhance the quality of the teaching-learning process. This is supported by the study of Ali et.al (2023), which stressed that these materials are used for more than just making class learning more engaging; they also serve to improve education quality, student skills, active student participation in the process, learning longevity, and the instillation of socially acceptable attitudes and behaviors in students.

The teacher is another factor in utilizing instructional practices. According to Popkova and Gulzat, (2020) to prepare pupils for the demands of today's workforce, teachers need to have certain qualities and competencies. The term "competence" refers to a broad range of skills, including knowledge, motivational and self-control traits, and beliefs. Eleje et al. (2022) claim that teaching calls for endurance, strength, adaptability, an open mind, and readiness. Furthermore, the proficiency and effectiveness of teachers determine the level of education. Learning will improve if teachers are well-qualified, driven, and dedicated to their work. The effectiveness of a teacher's job directly affects the extent of knowledge that students acquire.

In addition to teachers' proficiency and effectiveness in teaching, teachers should also possess the necessary skills in choosing and utilizing instructional practices. Labisig and Baluyos (2023), stated that in the twenty-first century, teachers must be flexible and adaptable to modify lesson plans, instructional materials, and activities to meet the diverse needs and learning preferences of their students

Identifying and dealing with student differences is another aspect of flexibility in teaching practices. To effectively assess student development, this could entail providing specific support, varied education, or a variety of evaluation techniques.

Aside from the teachers' competencies, proficiency, effectivity, and skills in teaching, according to Labisig and Baluyos (2023) another quality that 21st century teachers should have is cultivating a culture of collaboration and mentorship among teachers. Exchanging best practices and encouraging teamwork could help students acquire the skills required of educators in the twenty-first century. Moreover, efficient communication is crucial in working with colleagues, as it allows for the sharing of concepts, group problem-solving, and the exchange of top techniques. It encourages collaboration, and cooperation as well as the formation of a professional community of learning inside the institution.

Furthermore, Tallavaara and Raitianen, (2020) stated that additional skills needed for a history teacher, as cited from the Finnish National Board of Education stressed that the skills required of history teachers are extensive, including content knowledge and an understanding of the nature of history and the construction of historical knowledge. Moreover, Filgona (2020) mentioned that conceptualizing teacher knowledge is a complex issue that involves understanding key underlying phenomena such as the process of teaching and learning, the concept of knowledge as well as the teacher's knowledge is put into action in the classroom. Moreover, Tuithof (2021) asserted that to relate the content knowledge of teachers more specifically to the context of their

teaching practice, Shulman (1987) proposed the concept of Pedagogical Content Knowledge as a specific and unique form of teachers' knowledge.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher utilized a qualitative research design. Creswell (2007) described the qualitative research technique as a process where the research problem is studied in its natural setting to understand people's beliefs, experiences, attitudes, behaviors, and interactions, as it generated non-numerical data.

In connection to this study, the researcher deemed that a qualitative approach is suitable because the researcher wanted to describe the experiences of Social Studies teachers in utilizing alternative instructional practices, the factors that influenced the teachers in selecting and utilizing instructional practices in teaching Philippine History as well as the 'how' of their experiences.

A transcendental phenomenological approach was applied in this study. Husserl (1931) identified the tenets of transcendental phenomenology, which Moustakas (1994) converted into a qualitative approach. The examination of the phenomena that affected an individual was the main goal of this phenomenological approach. The transcendental phenomenology approach was suitable for this study because it sought to understand the lived experiences of teachers in teaching Philippine History which explained the essence of their experience. In addition, transcendental phenomenology was chosen as an appropriate methodology because the aim was to search for a meaningful understanding of Social Studies teachers' experiences in utilizing alternative instructional practices.

Participants

The research study was conducted at the National Capital Region DepEd Division of Caloocan, Philippines in six (6) schools. The participants of the study were selected through purposive sampling technique. This research study involved nine (9) elementary teachers. The participants were selected based on the criteria set by the researcher which include: 1.) a bachelor's degree in education; 2.) at least 5-10 years' experience teaching in the elementary grades; 3.) a public-school teacher; 4.) an implementor of Elementary K-12 Social Studies Curriculum for at least 5 years; and 5.) willingness to participate in the study.

Procedure

To accomplish this research study the researcher utilized research tools. These research tools include:

First, are the semi-structured interview guide questions as the primary instrument of the study. The semi-structured guide questions were patterned on Moustakas (1994). The semi structured interview guide question was submitted to the researcher's adviser, then was subjected to a trial with teachers in the elementary grades teaching Philippine History. The central questions in the semi-structured interviews focused attention on data gathering that led to the list of experiences and their descriptions, and a structural description on the experiences, and ultimately provide an understanding of the common experiences of the participants.

Second, is the document analysis. The researcher asked for a copy of lesson plans from the participants. The purpose of this research tool is to review and analyze the contents and the instructional practices the participants utilized in teaching Philippine History.

Third, is the researcher's reflective journal. The researcher also utilized a reflective journal to record the researcher's reactions, emotions, and thoughts during her interview with the participants.

To ensure the validity and reliability of the data collected through the semi-structured, the document analysis of the participants' lesson plans and researcher's reflective journal were used for a triangulation method.

Data Analysis

In analyzing the qualitative data, the researchers followed the steps of Moustakas (1994) concerning transcendental phenomenology which includes:

First, horizontalization the initial stage of analysis according to Moustakas (1994), the process of horizontalization involves identifying key statements, aligning them in a parallel fashion, and eliminating any repeats or overlaps. After reading and rereading the participant interview transcript, the researcher underlined the key terms associated with the phenomena. Reduction and removal were the next actions.

Second, developing clusters of meaning from the relevant statements into themes. This approach was used to determine whether the statements chosen during the horizontalization process contributed to the understanding of the phenomenon.

Third, writing the textural description, at this point, is grouping noteworthy statements into themes that correspond with the "what" of the experiences, textural qualities. Fourth, involves creating the structural description, which describes the setting or context that affected how the participants experienced the phenomenon, the conditions that must be met for something to appear, and possible structures of space, time, materiality, causality, and relationships to oneself and others.

Fifth, the process involved identifying the essence. The researcher combined textural and structural descriptions to create a descriptive passage that focused on the participants' shared experiences, essentially presenting the "essence" of the phenomenon.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher made sure that informed consent and issues of privacy and confidentiality were observed in the conduct of this research study.

The researcher guaranteed that participants were aware of the risks and rewards so they could choose whether to participate. The researcher informed the participants of the research subject, the kinds of questions the researcher will be asked, as well as how the data would be handled and used, to make certain ethical considerations in this research study.

For every piece of personal information should be as anonymous as possible to ensure privacy and secrecy. Information about how data were kept private were provided to the participants.

Results and Discussion

This qualitative study utilized the transcendental phenomenological approach to find the answers to problems and a deeper understanding of the lived experiences of Social Studies teachers in utilizing alternative instructional practices in teaching Philippine History. Based on the analysis of the semi-structured interview the study revealed nine (9) themes which include:

First, Social Studies teachers utilized alternative instructional practices through student centered activities and computer-aided methods. Most participants expressed that they used student-centered instructional practices in combination, which included group activity, reporting, dramatization, field trips, and debate. These alternative instructional practices they utilized involve students' participation and collaboration. This proved that participants of the study do not just rely on traditional instructional practices or teacher-centered teaching strategies in teaching Philippine History in the elementary grades, but they utilize alternative instructional practices/student centered activities to promote student's interests and learning in the subject. This is a breakthrough in the teaching of Philippine History which is usually described as teacher-centered which make it dull, and boring. This was supported by Zaka and Muhammad, (2021) as they emphasized that pupils who are actively engaged in the classroom demonstrate their enthusiasm and interest in what they are studying, actively participate in class discussions, and give their all during class activities.

Also revealed in this study that teachers utilized technology and computer-aided methodology specifically video clips which helped them to teach the subject. The participants' utilization of social media through video clips via YouTube was supported by Aydogmus et al. (2023), which stressed that there was enough, practical, and helpful educational content on social media. In addition, Aydogmus et al. (2023) study revealed how social media incorporates learning through reinforcement, improves retention, and makes the lesson entertaining.

Second, alternative instructional practices promote effective teaching and learning. As revealed in the semi-structured interviews, utilizing alternative instructional practices promotes understanding and retention of the lessons, promotes students' positive behavior toward Philippine History, good results and remarks from students, and fostered effective teaching. Furthermore, the participants experienced that in utilizing alternative instructional practices students could be able to relate and apply what they learn in the real life-situations which makes history easy to learn and promotes retention which is considered a remarkable experience. These experiences of the participants were supported by Alic and Bual (2021) as they stressed that the top best practices in the teaching and learning process of Philippines History were connecting the lesson to current social issues and the use of technology and multimedia tools in teaching. Moreover, by incorporating current events and pertinent knowledge into their everyday lives, they foster students' drive and curiosity.

The experiences of teachers in utilizing alternative instructional practices also developed students' positive behavior toward Philippine History. The study revealed that students were excited, motivated, and interested as expounded by the participants in their responses. These revelations of the teachers deviate from the common belief that Philippine history is a dull, and boring subject as mentioned by the two participants of the study. Moreover, alternative instructional practices utilized by Social Studies teachers promote students' positive behavior. This positive behavior of students towards the subject made them focused and interested which led to the acquisition of knowledge and understanding of the lesson. This notion was also supported by the study of Zaka and Muhammad (2021) about instructional effectiveness in history classrooms based on students' perception of the instructional practices of university teachers identified three significant dimensions include: students' engagement, instructional practices, and classroom management. The findings of the research study revealed that most students perceive that teachers used a variety of techniques to motivate students who showed low interest in the class (Zaka & Muhammad, 2021).

In addition, teachers also experienced that utilization of alternative instructional practices provided good results and feedback from the assessment of students which reflects the effectiveness of the alternative instructional practices based on high scores of students in the quizzes as well as the enjoyment and excitement of the students.

Lastly, as reflected in the responses of the participants in the semi-structured interview, teachers experience that alternative instructional practices foster effective teaching as the participants stressed that by utilizing alternative instructional practices, they

achieve their learning objectives. They also mentioned that they found fulfillment in teaching and history teaching became easy which they considered remarkable experiences.

Third, the experiences of Social Studies teachers also affect them as a teacher and their teaching. From their experiences in utilizing alternative instructional practices, the participants stressed that they developed a passion for teaching and professionalism. Most of the participants mentioned that they became patient, hardworking, and challenged due to their experiences which developed their positive outlook towards teaching. Furthermore, based on their experiences they took the initiative to improve their instructional practices to achieve their objectives which they considered as a manifestation that they fulfilled their goal in teaching. These experiences of teachers towards utilizing instruction practices were described by Olumremi and Oyewole (2013, cited in Eleje et al., 2022) as professionalism, which entails feeling behavior and dedication to the work or career. In addition, they also emphasized that teachers' performance would undoubtedly be productive if they had been dedicated and had a positive attitude. Having a positive attitude involves maintaining an optimistic outlook and considering the larger good regardless of the situation.

Fourth, a positive impact of teachers to students' learning and well-being. The semi structured interview revealed that utilizing alternative instructional practices resulted to the students' learning and appreciation to their teachers. Students shown appreciation through positive attitudes toward their teachers, and they were encouraged to do their best, due to the quality of learning they acquired which led to the promotion of students' well-being. For their co-teachers, the participants expressed that their experiences in utilizing alternative instructional practices promoted collaboration. These notable stories and experiences of elementary Social Studies teachers about their experiences in teaching were supported by Eleje et al. (2022) which claim that teaching is a difficult and complex professional activity. It calls for endurance, strength, adaptability, an open mind, and readiness. Furthermore, the proficiency and effectiveness of teachers determine the level of education. Learning will improve if teachers are well-qualified, driven, and dedicated to their work. The effectiveness of a teacher's job directly affects the extent of knowledge that students acquire.

Fifth, promotes teachers' collaboration, open communication, and open-mindedness to share and accept ideas from others to improve instructional practices. Based on the experiences of the participants communication was very important as they shared their experiences. This belief was brought out by Labisig and Baluyos (2023) in their study as they expressed that efficient communication is crucial in working with colleagues, as it allows for the sharing of concepts, group problem-solving, and the exchange of top techniques. It encourages collaboration, and cooperation as well as the formation of a professional community of learning inside the institution.

Sixth, problems and challenges experienced by the Social Studies teachers in utilizing alternative instructional practices. As revealed in the semi-structured interview, most of the participants encountered problems in utilizing alternative instructional practices which include ineffective instructional practices, participants shared that they need to change their strategy from time to time to cater students' needs and interests. The lack of instructional and learning materials is another problem. Problems regarding lack of instructional materials were also revealed in the study of Sumaljag's (2020) which stressed that teachers struggled with the lack of textbooks, activity sheets, and other learning resources. These claims were also mentioned in a study conducted in 2024 by Awa-ao and Roperez, who discovered that a lack of learning resources and a scarcity of Philippine historical books made it difficult for participants to comprehend and carry out the lessons. Another challenge according to the participants is instructional time. In the K-12 curriculum, the instructional time for Social Studies is 40 minutes, the participants mentioned that it's not enough for them to finish their lessons due to so many topics to discuss wherein the allotted time for the subject is only 40 minutes. When it comes to limited instructional time in teaching Philippine History, Ozyildirim (2022) emphasized that learning duration is thought to be one of the most significant influencing aspects when discussing a person's specific learning status. It is widely held that increasing study time is bound to result in improved academic achievements. Lastly, the participants also encountered students' collaboration issues and personal concerns among students when it comes to group activities and collaborative works. The problems in students' attitudes and learning which led to collaboration issues were emphasized by Ali (2023) as he pointed out that teachers experience difficulties in managing the interaction as students do not follow the norms of interaction. Thus, teachers should do their best to make the classroom conducive to learning wherein all students are included and recognized in the activities to maintain harmonious relationships.

Seventh, elements of teaching and learning are the factors Social Studies teachers consider in selecting and utilizing alternative instructional practices these include: 1.) the internal stakeholders of the school, the students, and teachers. As revealed in the responses of the participants, 8 out of 9 considered first and foremost the learner as an important factor they consider in choosing/utilizing alternative instructional practices. The reasons for such factors were centered on students' abilities and level of understanding and learning. In addition, based on the statements of the participants they believed that in selecting and utilizing instructional practices teachers' readiness, mastery of the subject matter, and the relevance of the subject matter should be taken into consideration; 2.) the instructional time, the participants believed that the time allotted for the instruction determines the attainment of the learning objectives and intended skills and knowledge; 3.) the classroom or learning space, should promote students' safety, welfare, comfort, and most all, conducive for the acquisition and transfer of learning; 4.) instructional and learning materials should be available, effective, and suited to the topic and activities and; 5.) the topic/lesson should be aligned with the learning objectives, accurate, relevant to the students, and students should easily understand or learn the lesson. The factors that Social Studies teachers considered in selecting and alternative utilizing instructional was supported by Ali et al (2023), as they stressed that the choice of a certain approach is influenced by the learning objectives, the subject matter, and the needs, interests, and capabilities of the students. Moreover, Ali et al

(2023) emphasized that learning materials and resources are facilities made available to teachers and students to support effective teaching and learning processes.

Eighth, students' motivational level and performance level were the contexts and situations that affected their experiences in utilizing alternative instructional practices. The motivational level involves students' feelings and emotions in class. This context or situation was dependent on the time the participants observed that students were motivated, excited, and interested. The participants need to be sensitive and aware of these emotions and behavior, so they can be flexible in their instructional practices as well as, these feelings and emotions serve as their gauge in knowing if a particular alternative instructional was effective or not. Another context was the performance level of students. The performance level of the students involved the set of students being fast, or slow learners as well as their group, if they belong to higher or lower section. This diversity of learners when it comes to their performance level and motivational level affected their utilization of alternative instructional practices which serve as a determinant of the effectiveness or ineffectiveness of the alternative instructional practices which develops teachers' flexibility and adaptability on what and how to use the alternative instructional practices.

Ninth, to improve the delivery of the lesson and to achieve good assessment results were the contexts and situations why most of the participants asked for suggestions from others. They consider the time and place such as appropriate alternative instructional practices to deliver the lesson impressively and properly during demonstration teachings and for students to sustain their interest throughout the demo-teaching and will guide them to understand the lesson that will lead to good results in students' assessment. As revealed and manifested in their answers, the participants ask suggestions from others because they recognized the expertise of their co-teachers.

In essence, the experiences of Social Studies teachers in utilizing alternative instructional practices are related to the contexts and situations teachers consider in utilizing alternative instructional practices. The research study revealed that the improvement of students' learning and interest towards Philippine History was the focus of teachers. With this notion, teachers need to consider the situations and contexts such as the performance level and motivational level of the students as they utilize alternative instructional practices. Knowledge of how students learn through their performance level determines what alternative instructional practices to utilize as well as awareness of the time when they are highly motivated will be the basis for teachers to be flexible and adaptive on what alternative instructional practices to utilize. Knowledge of such contexts and situations will lead to students' understating of Philippine History and promote a positive attitude of students toward the subject which was described by teachers as their lived experiences in utilizing instructional practices. With this essence, it is relevant for teachers to understand the performance and motivational level of the students which will serve as their basis to what alternative instructional practices they will utilize for the students to understand and learn Philippine History as well as to have positive behavior towards the subject.

Conclusions

The researcher came up with the following conclusions:

Alternative instructional practices focused on student-centered activities that were utilized by the Social Studies teacher in teaching Philippine History promoted positive behavior of students towards the subject, developed students' understanding and retention, improved assessment results of students, and fostered effective teaching.

Utilizing alternative instructional practices strengthened teachers' work ethics and professionalism as well as improved students' well-being.

Teachers considered lack of instructional and learning materials, insufficient instruction time, and students' attitude problems as challenges and problems in teaching Philippine History. There is a need to address these problems and challenges because teachers in the study consider these as essential elements in teaching and learning, the factors that they consider in selecting and utilizing alternative instructional practices.

Students' motivational and performance levels were the contexts and situations that influenced the teachers in utilizing alternative instructional practices. The diversity of students in terms of their performance and motivation requires teachers to be flexible and adaptative to cater for the different performance and motivational levels of students. Teachers were vulnerable on how students learn, encouraged them to seek help from their co-teachers which promoted collaboration and mentoring among teachers for the improvement of teaching Philippine History.

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